

FEATURES OF THE GENRES OF FICTION AND FANTASY IN MODERN LITERATURE

R.A. Asanov

Teacher of the Department of Uzbek Language and Language Teaching
at the Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: Fiction and fantasy are two genres of modern literature that transport the reader to amazing and exciting worlds. In fiction, authors explore the scientific, technological and social aspects of the future, presenting us with new technologies, planets and races. While fantasy, takes us into magical worlds where magic, epic battles and fantastic creatures are everywhere.

Modern literature offers a wide range of works in these genres that allow the reader to get carried away and expand their imagination. In modern literature, fiction and fantasy have become a platform for discussing complex social and philosophical issues. They offer readers the opportunity to explore themes such as power, faith, tolerance, justice, and the meaning of life. They also raise questions about our own world and possible future scenarios.

In modern literature, fiction and fantasy are not only entertaining but also thought-provoking. They allow the reader to immerse themselves in a world of imagination where anything is possible, and to experience emotions and adventures that are not found in everyday life.

Key words: Fiction, fantasy, magic and sorcery, science fiction, post-apocalyptic, cyberpunk, social fiction, fantasy humor, action fiction, steampunk, epic fantasy, gothic fantasy, heroic fantasy.

Modern literature offers a wide range of works in these genres that allow the reader to be captivated and expand their imagination. This paper is about the differences and characteristics of the science fiction and fantasy genres in modern literature, an understanding of which is necessary when writing research papers in these genres.

In modern literature, there are two genres that many people not infrequently confused with each other, they are the genres of fiction and fantasy.

I think many would agree that modern literature cannot do without these two genres. Both of these genres have resonated in the hearts of many and are popular all over the world.

Fiction is a genre of literature, film, art and entertainment that focuses on creating previously unseen, fictional worlds, events and characters that are different from reality. It often includes elements of science fiction, fantasy, horror, and other genres.

Fiction can explore futuristic or alternate realities, scientific and technological breakthroughs, interaction with alien civilizations, time and space travel, magic and mythology, and social and political issues.

This genre allows authors and creators to express their imagination and explore various ideas, concepts, and dramatic plots that may be impossible or unimaginable in the real world. Fiction can also serve as a means of commenting on contemporary issues and challenges, as well as exploring human nature and potential. Fiction works can range from light and entertaining to deeply philosophical and provocative. They inspire readers and viewers to think and raise questions about the future of humanity and the nature of our reality.

Fiction is hugely popular around the world and has influenced culture, science and technology. It offers us a unique opportunity to immerse ourselves in fantasy worlds and explore the boundaries of possibility and imagination.

The fantasy genre is interesting for many reasons. It allows authors and readers to escape from reality and plunge into a world of magic, fantasy and adventure. Fantasy can help the imagination soar, and thrilling battles and epic adventures can evoke many emotional reactions in the reader. Fantasy often contains valuable lessons and morals, such as the struggle for good and justice, and the ideals of self-sacrifice and overcoming adversity. In addition, fantasy can be an effective tool for telling stories about current social issues and conflicts, showing them through allegorical imagery and creating one unique world. Overall, fantasy is a genre that can enrich our imagination, improve our reflective thinking and analytical skills, as well as allowing us to enjoy beautiful and compelling stories.¹

The fantasy genre is also an extremely popular genre not only in fiction but also in films and computer games, where a fictional world is described, and in it there is magic and sorcery, as well as various fairy tale creatures like elves, fairies, demons, dragons, dwarves, orcs and other fictional characters. In fantasy worlds,

usually describe the struggle between good and evil, and often feature heroes and heroines who try to resist the villains and protect their world. Also, fantasy worlds may feature different races and cultures, each with their own traditions and customs.

The fantasy genre is often associated with medieval Europe, as many works describe worlds that resemble medieval Europe, with its castles, knights and kings. However, fantasy worlds can also contain elements of modernity, for example in the form of technology or socio-cultural phenomena. For example, people used to dream of creating a car that would drive itself, or a computer, or virtual glasses, people dreamed about it, it was from the category of fantasy at that time, but now all this already exists in reality. Let's take a closer look at the fantasy genre.

The fantasy genre has many features that make it unique and interesting to readers and viewers. Some of the main features of the genre include:

Fictional world: fantasy worlds are often described by authors as fictional, with magic, fairy tale creatures, and places that do not exist in the real world.

Battle between good and evil: many fantasy works describe a battle between good and evil, with heroes and heroines fighting against villains to protect their world.

Diversity of races and cultures: fantasy worlds often contain many different races and cultures, each with their own unique traditions, customs, and languages.

Magic and sorcery: fantasy worlds are often saturated with magic and sorcery, which can be used by both good and evil characters.

Fairy tale elements: fantasy worlds often contain elements from fairy tales and legends, such as princesses, dragons, sorcerers, and other fairy tale creatures.

Medieval culture: many works in the fantasy genre describe worlds that resemble medieval Europe, with its castles, knights and kings.

It should also be noted the complete freedom of the author, he can turn the plot in the most unexpected way, because the magical world of fantasy suggests that everything is possible in it. This last feature is one of the most important, defining. It clearly distinguishes fantasy and science fiction, because science fiction describes the probable, and the author is constrained by certain limits. He is forced to give an explanation for the improbable, to justify scientifically or pseudoscientifically (which is most often the case)².

In general, the fantasy genre offers readers and viewers a unique world where everything is possible and where only imagination is the limit.

At this stage of development of literature, it is enriched with various genres that every person can find what his heart lies to. Thanks to literature, a person enriches his own world, expands his worldview.

Fantasy literature is a genre that describes fictional worlds, creatures and technologies that do not exist in the real world. The genre of fiction includes many subgenres and trends, each with its own characteristics and features. Below I will discuss in more detail some of the most common subgenres of science fiction literature:

Science Fiction: a genre that describes scientific and technological advances that can be achieved in the future. This genre may also include time and space travel.

Fantasy: a genre that describes magical creatures, worlds, and events that do not obey the laws of physics. This genre often includes epic battles and quests.

Horror: a genre that describes scary and macabre events and creatures. This genre often uses elements of the supernatural and mystical.

Post-apocalyptic: a genre that describes the world after a disaster, such as a nuclear war or epidemic. This genre often has elements of survival and a struggle for resources.

Cyberpunk: a genre that describes a world where technology has reached a high level but society is in decline. This genre often features cyberspace and cyberpunks.

Social fiction: a genre that describes a future society in which new social, political, and economic systems exist.

Fantastic humor: a genre that combines elements of science fiction and comedy.

Alternate history: a genre that describes a world in which historical events have occurred that are different from those that have occurred in the real world.

Action fiction, space opera, paranormal romance, and steampunk are really additional sub-genres of fantasy literature.

Action fiction: a genre that combines elements of action and science fiction. The main characters in this genre are often fighters or soldiers who fight enemies to save the world or galaxy.

Space opera: a genre that describes the adventures of space travelers and their relationships. This genre often contains elements of science fiction and fantasy.

Paranormal romance: a genre that combines romance and paranormal phenomena such as vampires, werewolves, spirits, etc. Fantasy and horror elements are often used in this genre.

Steampunk: a genre that describes an alternate reality in which technology developed primarily on steam, mechanics, and analog devices. This genre often contains elements of adventure and action.

Fantasy is one of the most common genres of fantasy literature that describes magical worlds and creatures that do not obey the laws of physics. Fantasy also has many sub-genres, each with its own characteristics and features. Some of the best known sub-genres of fantasy include:

Epic fantasy: a genre that describes grand adventures and epic battles in a world populated by magical creatures and heroes.

Heroic fantasy: a genre that describes stories of heroes who fight for justice and the defense of their loved ones in a world populated by magical creatures.

Medieval fantasy: a genre that describes a world resembling the Middle Ages, with magical creatures and events.

Gothic fantasy: a genre that describes a dark world filled with horrors and mystical creatures.

Fantasy romance: a genre that combines elements of romance and fantasy.

Dark fantasy: a genre that describes a world filled with violence and horror, with a more mature style and themes than other fantasy subgenres.

Fantasy comedy: A genre that combines elements of comedy and fantasy.

These are just some of the most common sub-genres of fantasy. There are also many other subgenres such as historical fantasy, fantasy for children and young adults, and heroic fantasy.

Historical fantasy: a genre that describes fictional events and characters in a historical context. This genre often utilizes elements of real historical events, characters, and cultural traits.

Fantasy for children and young adults: a genre that describes magical worlds and adventures for young readers. This genre often contains elements of adventure, fantasy, and morality.

Heroic fantasy: a genre that describes heroic adventures in which the main characters fight for justice and the protection of their loved ones. This genre often uses elements of magic and fantasy.

In conclusion, we can say that the genre of fiction and fantasy allow us to immerse ourselves in a world of magic, myths and fantasy, and discover unlimited possibilities. In sci-fi we explore scientific and technological advances, imagine the future and consider the existence of extraterrestrial life, time and space travel, artificial intelligence and more. Fantasy, on the other hand, opens us up to worlds of magic, folklore and mythology where we encounter epic creatures, heroes and battles between good and evil. Both genres allow us to see that there are many more possibilities than we can imagine and inspire us to dream and believe in miracles. They offer us unique and compelling stories that not only entertain, but also make us think about our own reality and what lies beyond our familiar world. And it is also hard to imagine modern literature without these two genres, they can also be called a kind of engine of progress, because many years ago what would have been considered fiction, is now a reality!

Literature:

1. Asanov R.A. // The usefulness and peculiarities of the genre identity of literature // Science and innovation international scientific journal volume 2 issue 12 - 2023. - C. 15-16. — DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10280783>
2. Gogoleva, S.A. Influence of the gothic novel on the fantasy genre and its role in the genre formation // Nauka i obrazovanie. - 2007. - № 3. - C. 166-167.
3. Fiction of the XX century in genre coverage / scientific dialog. - 2017. - № 6. - C. 148-157. — DOI: 10.24224/2227-1295-2017-6-148157. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/fantastika-nachala-hh-veka-v-zhanrovomosveschenii>
4. Alekseev S. V. / Fantasy / Moscow Humanities University / <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/fentezi>
5. Mzareulov K. Fiction. General course / Chapter 1 Fiction as a genre. What is fiction? / https://www.gumer.info/bibliotek_Buks/Literat/mzar/01.php